

×*Patrocereus*, a New Nothogenus in Cactaceae

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER

Abstract—The nothogenus ×*Patrocereus* (= *Pachycereus* × *Mitrocereus*) and the new combination ×*Patrocereus apicicostatus* are proposed.

The name ×*Pachebergia apicicostata* was published in 2008 for a naturally occurring hybrid between *Backebergia militaris* and *Pachycereus pecten-aboriginum*. Since the first species is often included in *Mitrocereus*, the corresponding nothogenus and combination are proposed:

×*Patrocereus* M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**

= *Mitrocereus* Backeb. × *Pachycereus* Britton & Rose

<https://www.cactusnames.org/patrocereus>

×*Patrocereus apicicostatus* (S.Arias & Terrazas) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**

≡ ×*Pachebergia apicicostata* S.Arias & Terrazas — *Revista Mex. Biodivers.*

79(1): 26 (-27; figs., map) (2008)

= *Mitrocereus militaris* (Audot) Bravo × *Pachycereus pecten-aboriginum*

(Engelm. ex S.Watson) Britton & Rose

<https://www.cactusnames.org/patrocereus-apicicostatus>

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER

ORCID 0000-0002-5182-9615

Roggekamp 379

NL-2592 VV Den Haag

m@vdm.nu